

Freeze-drying as *Chromobacterium violaceum*'s Preservation Method for the BIXO Mission

Martín Blanco Prego, Xavier Manuel De Rada Piñeiro, Manuel Diz-Folgar
UVigo SpaceLab

Faculty Advisor: Daniel García-Lojo

CINBIO, Universidade de Vigo, Campus Universitario As Lagoas, Marcosende, Vigo, 36310 Spain

danielgarcia@uvigo.es

ABSTRACT

Over the past few years, the space sector has witnessed a growing interest in exploring how biological organisms, such as *Escherichia coli* or *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, respond to high radiation and microgravity environments. Among the various biological space missions, CubeSats, particularly SmallSats, have emerged as a popular platform for conducting such experiments owing to their reduced size and cost-effectiveness, which allows for the integration of miniaturized labs to study microorganisms onboard. However, the biggest challenge facing such missions is the preservation of living organisms for extended periods before the start of the experiments.

The UVigo SpaceLab team is currently developing a CubeSat mission called BIXO (Bacteriological Intercommunication eXperiment in Orbit) to study the impact of prolonged exposure to radiation and microgravity in the space environment on the cell-to-cell communication process of *Chromobacterium violaceum*. The mission involves conducting three rounds of experiments on this bacteria over nine months, which requires the preservation of the bacteria in a dormant state for long periods. Therefore, successful preservation is a critical requirement for the mission's success.

This paper aims to explore the current state of the art in preserving biological microorganisms for space missions, with a particular focus on the BIXO mission. It will introduce the freeze-drying method as a powerful alternative for preserving *C. violaceum* cells and maintaining their viability for the mission. Additionally, it will detail the entire experimental process for obtaining the lyophilized samples of the bacteria, including the integration of the lyophiles into the satellite and an assessment of their viability.

INTRODUCTION

Biological missions onboard SmallSats have experienced a notable increase in number as a result of the progressive reduction of cost of launch and development of the last decades. Specifically, CubeSats have been the most prolific platform among SmallSats for biological applications, as the ratio of volume/cost is the most suitable and competitive for this sort of missions.

During the last two decades, NASA has launched a total of six biological CubeSats, though BioSentinel is currently in its journey to an heliocentric orbit and its results are yet to be obtained. Furthermore, there are also other bio satellites in development using the CubeSat standard which have not already been launched, like AcubeSAT, from SpaceDot, HEXON,

from the University of Toronto Aerospace Team or BIXO, from UVigo SpaceLab - all of them teams of students.

All of these biological missions require a preservation method to ensure microorganisms onboard the satellite are maintained alive for the period between the integration and the beginning of the experiment. This time interval may take several months, so the critical point of these missions lies in the success of the preservation of the biological payload.

Among others, freeze-dry desiccation has been considered for preserving *Chromobacterium violaceum* bacteria samples in the BIXO mission, as it has shown good viability results in previous studies.

To this aim, this document will gather different preservation methods used in previous biological missions and discuss why freeze-drying desiccation remains the optimal for the requirements of the BIXO mission.

THE BIXO MISSION

BIXO, Bacteriological Intercommunication eXperiment in Orbit, is the biological mission developed by UVigo SpaceLab, a team of students from the University of Vigo. The goal of this mission is to determine the role of microgravity and prolonged exposure to space radiation in the *Quorum Sensing* (QS) process over a period of nine months.¹

QS is a bacterial cell-to-cell communication process that involves the production, detection and response to extracellular signaling molecules known as autoinducers (AIs). Apart from activating the expression of genes beneficial for cooperative actions, the detection of AIs (which takes place in the cytoplasm or in the membrane receptors) produces a feed-forward loop in the production of AI. That is, when bacteria cells detect AIs they produce more AIs, which is the cause behind the synchrony of the entire bacterial population.²

Typically, *Chromobacterium violaceum* has been chosen for studying QS as this gram-negative bacteria produces a violet pigment as a result of this intercommunication process. This pigment is called violacein and is suggested to be a respiratory bioactive molecule. The success of the use of *C. violaceum* in lab experiments lies in the ease of detection and quantification of their characteristic QS-regulated trait, together with multiple biological applications it has been reported to have. Namely, anti-proliferative activity against cancer cells, anti-gram-positive bacterial activity, antifungal activity, anti-leishmanial property, etc.³

As a result of this ease of quantification of the QS in *C. violaceum*, and the multiple medical applications of this pigment, a better understanding of cell-to-cell communication processes will be invaluable for the space race that is currently being promoted worldwide. This is the reason for the 9-month duration of the mission, as it coincides with the estimated time of a manned rocket trip from Earth to Mars. During that journey, bacterial behavior takes on an important role in the success of the mission itself, as it directly affects the crew members.

In order to successfully achieve significant results on the role of radiation and microgravity in the QS, the mission is divided into phases and batches. Firstly, the

Launch and Early Operations Phase (LEOP) takes place for a few hours after the deployment of the satellite, until the first contact with the Ground Segment is established. Right after that, the Commissioning phase is performed to ensure that all the subsystems and payloads work according to the specifications, which can take around two weeks. Thirdly, the satellite enters into the Main Science Phase, which is divided into five sub-phases. These are, in order of procedure: De-lyophilisation Sub-phase, during which the growth medium will be pumped to the bacteria reservoir to take them out of the freeze-dried state; the Experiment Batch Sub-phase, in which absorbance measurements will be taken from several micro-wells where the bacteria will grow; Waiting Period Sub-phase, which is used for extracting conclusions about the first batch and make any suitable change for the correct execution of the second one. After this, the Technology Demonstration Phase begins, a period lasting up to the last month of the nominal mission time, in which secondary payloads are tested and the data of the last batch is reviewed. Finally, at the Long Term Storage Experiment Phase, a third batch of the bacteria is rehydrated for determining the effects of prolonged exposure to radiation.

In summary, the bacteria from the last batch must resist in stasis state for a period of 9 months plus the time between payload integration into the satellite and the launch. To this aim, a proper preservation method is demanded.

STATE OF THE ART: PRESERVATION OF MICROORGANISMS IN PREVIOUS SPACE MISSIONS

Up to date, the only microorganisms that have been launched to space inside SmallSats are *Escherichia coli*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Bacillus subtilis* and *Halorubrum chaoviatoris*.

By far, the first pair has been the most prolific biological organisms to fly to space, as *E. coli* has been present in the first biological CubeSat, GeneSat (2006), and in EcAMSat, while the *S. cerevisiae* has been used in the PharmaSat mission, is currently involved in the BioSentinel mission and will soon return to LEO (Low Earth Orbit) onboard the AcubeSat satellite. On the other hand, *B. subtilis* was part of the payload of the O/OREOS SESLO mission together with *H. chaoviatoris*.^{4,5}

Regarding the preservation method applied for the different organisms, GeneSat opted for a “stasis buffer” for embedding the *E. coli* until the satellite had reached a stable orbit.⁶ Although no further information about the content of that buffer is given, papers concerning the EcAMSat mission mention the use of the M9 buffer,

a “minimal salts” medium containing 22 mM KH_2PO_4 , 42 mM Na_2HPO_4 , 8.5 mM NaCl, 19 mM NH_4Cl , 1 mM MgSO_4 , and 0.01 mM CaCl_2 .⁷ The estimated delay time between the integration and the initiation of the experiments was of around 6 weeks, therefore, test were conducted for a period of 10 weeks, which showed viability of 0,7% in the wild type strain.⁸

That stasis buffer method was also applied to budding yeast cells (*S. cerevisiae*) in the PharmaSat mission (though its content is unknown), which had a delay of 75% of the nominal stasis period length, which resulted in 6-7 weeks of stasis.⁹ In contrast, for the BioSentinel mission, which also studies budding yeast, air-drying was chosen as the optimal preservation method for a mission with a nominal duration of 6-12 months and an extra pre-launch period of ~12 months. The desiccation process was performed along three days in an incubator at 23 °C and 20-30% relative humidity (R.H.). Once the samples were dry, they were stored at stable 23 °C and 0% R.H. conditions. Although vacuum-drying and freeze-drying processes were also tested, air-drying resulted in the highest post-desiccation survival.¹⁰

In the case of *H. chaoviatoris* and *B. subtilis*, alike in BioSentinel, these specimens were air-dried for O/OREOS satellite, which ended to enable storage of specimens for longer duration than a wet stasis medium. According to the ground tests performed before integration, air-dry preserved organisms presented survival of more than eight months.¹¹

LYOPHILISATION AS A PRESERVATION METHOD FOR *C. VIOLACEUM*

Although the duration of the pre-launch stage of satellite missions mostly depends on delays coming from the launcher availability, which are homogeneous for all of them, the BIXO mission counts with an extra disadvantage in terms of bacteriological viability, since the duration of the experiment is significantly longer than the others.

GeneSat-1, PharmaSat, O/OREOS, SporeSat and EcAMSat had mission lifetimes between 2 weeks and ~3 months, which is a time frame similar to the period before the Technology Demonstration Phase of BIXO, when the first two batches of *C. violaceum* will be rehydrated and studied. However, the induced stasis state in the bacteria can not only guarantee viability until that date, but must also achieve a nine-month survival under space environment conditions. The only mission that has a similar duration is BioSentinel (12-18 months), but the reasons given by NASA Ames Research Center to justify the adoption of air-drying as the optimal preservation method for *S. cerevisiae* can not be extrapolated to BIXO, as the microorganisms

studied are significantly different (eukaryotic and prokaryotic cells, with the yeasts capability of forming spores, which *Chromobacterium violaceum* does not have) and the mission requirements are also different (deep space vs LEO environment).

Chromobacterium violaceum's inability to form spores and the impossibility of constant supply of fresh media leave the inactivation of the bacteria as the unique viable option for their preservation. This can be achieved by numerous ways, including cryopreservation, spray drying, vacuum drying or freeze drying.

Cryopreservation consists of the freezing of the culture in very low temperatures after being suspended in a cryoprotectant media which inhibits the formation of ice crystals that may kill the cells. This method requires constant -80°C temperature so it is not suited for this mission. Freezing the bacteria normally in a lab also requires the sample to be plated in solid media and only then it is able to be inoculated in liquid media by taking a small piece of a colony. Then to be repeatable this first culture is denominated “preinoculum” and taken a fixed amount from it, so the same amount of cells is used in every batch. This is the conservation method for both strands used in the lab experiments.^{12, 13}

Spray drying consists of the expulsion of the bacterial culture in a protective buffer through a nozzle that transforms the culture into droplets that are dried and collected in a chamber in a dust-like form that can be rehydrated and reactivated. The principal inconvenience of this method is the specific machinery we do not have access to, and the survivability of the bacteria. In this method bacteria are put through a high mechanical stress which gram positive bacteria can withstand better, but that is not the case of *Chromobacterium violaceum* that, as it was mentioned above, it is a gram negative bacteria.¹²

Vacuum drying uses pressure reduction to remove water from the samples and leaving the bacteria inactive, being able to survive long storage times. The problem of this method is the sensibility of the bacteria to the anoxic environment and the mechanical damage the cells may suffer if the vacuum is not set correctly as water starts to boil at room temperature while saturation pressure diminishes.¹²

Freeze drying, which is the selected technique, uses a combination of the cryopreservation and the vacuum drying. The freezing traps the bacteria so the mechanical damage is not produced and reduces its metabolism by decreasing the nutrients needed while the vacuum drying is performed. This approach lets the bacteria suffer less from both the mechanical damage

and the metabolic requirements. Freeze drying also results in a powder-like product that, under the right conditions, can be stored for more than a decade. The main critical condition is the humidity, that if it is not low enough can lead into the bacteria reactivation and the progressive viability loss of the lyophile. The reactivation of this preservation method consists of the resuspension on suitable growth media, which is ideal in the raised mission.^{12, 14}

LYOPHILE INTEGRATION IN THE BIXO CUBESAT

The reservoir containing the bacteria lyophiles will be integrated inside a pressurized container at approximately 810.6 - 1215.9 hPa, occupying an entire Cubesat unit. Inside this container, electronic devices and microfluidic hardware will share space closely. Therefore, in order to maintain the freeze-dried samples in stasis state onboard BIXO (2U CubeSat), the storage device used must isolate the housed lyophiles from external humidity and contamination. In case some of the nutrient medium gets undesirably in touch with the bacteria samples, a whole batch of experiments will be spoiled. In addition, this device shall meet crucial requirements, such as being chemically inert and non-bactericidal, to prevent killing the bacteria; and withstanding temperatures from 0 °C to 30 °C, to resist multiple environmental conditions.

Polymer bags were at first considered for storing the lyophiles as they were watertight and could easily adapt to reduced spaces. However, due to difficulties in introducing minimal amounts of freeze-dried bacteria inside them, we sought a more suitable alternative. Overall, we selected Fluidic 639 and Fluidic 934 tanks as they had ideal characteristics for storing freeze-dried bacteria. Despite the different internal volumes of the tanks (500 µL and 200 µL, respectively), both models were virtually identical and were made of high-quality materials, ensuring the protection of the bacteria.

It is noteworthy that the fluidic tanks that were selected possess a characteristic that bears resemblance to Eppendorf tubes. This indicates the potential for direct bacteria lyophilisation within the fluidic tank, as small volumes of liquid are easier and faster to freeze-dry. This technical breakthrough holds the promise of enhancing the lyophilisation technique while minimizing the possibility of sample contamination during the transfer process from lyophilisation devices to on-orbit storage.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCESS

Lyophilisation consists of sample drying by exposing the bacteria to vacuum while keeping them frozen. This

produces the sublimation of the water in the bacteria, thus leaving them in a dormant state where metabolism is cut down so the limit cells do not need nutrients nor their optimal temperature to be kept alive through storage periods. This is how cells can be preserved until the moment the experiment is triggered, ensuring the survival of the cells and the success of the mission.

This process implies the preparation of *Chromobacterium violaceum* cultures at the beginning of its exponential growth phase, as it ensures the maximum metabolic activity at the same time that minimizes the number of dead cells in the culture. To achieve this while keeping repeatability ensured for results of every batch of lyophiles, a long experimental process is followed throughout ~3 days, which includes a pre-inoculum of the bacteria to standardize the amount of cells in the inoculum.

Pre-inoculum

The first step of the experiment involved inoculating a cryopreserved *C. violaceum* glycerol onto a pair of Petri dishes (just for redundancy) containing Luria Bertani (LB) Agar medium. LB Agar medium was prepared by adding 10 g of triptone, 5 g of yeast extract, 5 g of NaCl, and 12 g of agar per 1 L. The inoculation was performed using a plastic bacterial loop and following the streak technique and the plates were then incubated at 30 °C.

After ~12 hours, when the colonies were easily spottable by sight, one of them was then taken from its respective Petri dish using another loop and was afterwards inoculated in individual 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks filled with 50 mL of LB medium (the same recipe described before for LB Agar but without agar). The pre-inoculum flasks were then left overnight inside a thermoregulated shaker at 30 °C and 220 RPM.

Inoculum

When ~11 hours had passed since the pre-inoculation, ultraviolet-visible (UV-Vis) measurements were periodically taken employing 1 cm square quartz cuvette. To avoid spectrophotometer saturation the pre-inoculum was diluted 5 times in LB to a final volume of 2 mL (400 µL pre-inoculum and 1600 µL of LB). In the first measurement, optical density (OD) at 600 nm was still at 0.367 AU (Arbitrary Units), far from ~1 AU, which was the goal for the inoculum, therefore, intervals of 20-25 minutes were left in between measurements to control the OD before reaching the aimed point. It was 14 hours after the pre-inoculum that the OD level was 0.972 AU, so it was decided to inoculate 500 µL in another 250 mL flask filled with 50 mL of LB (1:101 dilution). In order to

calculate the error of the OD measures that form the bacterial growth curve, this inoculation was performed by triplicate (named as N1, N2, and N3). Also, another set of three flasks were prepared in order to perform the extractions for the lyophilisation (labeled L1, L2, and L3). The six flasks, with cellulose stoppers to prevent contamination, were introduced into the thermo-regulated orbital shaker at the same temperature and angular velocity parameters (30 °C and 220 RPM) for 13 hours.

Figure 1: Picture of the six inoculum flasks prior to introducing them into the shaker for 13 hours. L1, L2 and L3 labeled red and N1, N2 and N3 labeled blue.

Measurements

During this time, spectra were taken around each half hour using the Agilent Cary 8454 spectrophotometer. First the blank (LB) was measured, and the own Cary 8454 software automatically subtracted it from the following measurements. Then, every 30 minutes, the UV-Vis spectra of the growth flasks (previously prepared by triplicate and labeled as N1, N2, and N3) was characterized). To this end, the corresponding flasks were temporarily taken out of the shaker and placed inside the Telstar Bio II Advance Plus laminar flow cabinet for extracting the correct volume of the inoculum and diluting it in LB. At first, the dilutions for the measurements were 1:5, but as the OD increased over time, higher dilutions were done to avoid saturating the spectrophotometer, as above ~1,5 AU the resultant measurement was corrupted. Due to this reason, dilutions were sequentially increased (1:5, 1:10, 1:20 and 1:50) as the OD level approached the upper limit of saturation.

Once the measure was performed, the flasks were returned to the shaker (30 °C and 220 RPM). After each measurement, the cuvettes were thoroughly cleaned to be prepared for the next one. For that, the cuvettes were filled first with water and later with ethanol (three times each), and finally cleaned with distilled water. The cuvettes were later turned face-down to remove the water droplets from inside and the exterior faces were dried using a special paper to prevent microfibers from getting attached to the surfaces. The resulting data from UV-Vis measurements was then extracted to the OriginPro software to their normalization in function of the dilution factor and to collect all the data together. Finally, employing the same software, the obtained OD values at 600 nm in function of the growing time were plotted, graphing the growth curve (Figure 2). It is important to note that data treatment was performed in parallel with the data acquisition to, in case of obtaining strange values, detect any possible mistake in the measurement protocol or in the dilution process and repeat the UV-Vis characterization of these points.

Concerning the growth curve of *C. violaceum* (Figure 2), it shows little evolution until the first 200 minutes have passed, when the growth rate becomes the highest as it reaches the exponential phase. This stage lasts for 200-250 minutes more, when the bacteria enter into the plateau phase, in which the population size remains constant. The relevance of this curve lies mainly in the ability to determine the growth status of another sample of *C. violaceum* simply by measuring its OD at 600 nm.

Pre-freezing operations

As it was mentioned before, another set of three growth flasks (labeled as L1, L2, and L3) were kept in the shaker (30 °C and 220 RPM) with the objective of freezing the samples once the culture growth had reached the exponential growth phase. As illustrated in Figure 2, this phase corresponds with values of OD at 600 nm of around 2 AU. For this reason, at this moment (around 250 min from the beginning), it was decided to start the operations prior to freezing the samples. At this point, two operations were executed in parallel: the pre-lyophilisation viability assessment preparation, and the suspension of the bacteria in the cryoprotectant.

Figure 2: Growth curve from mean values of N1, N2 and N3 samples of *C. violaceum*. The red line represents the sigmoidal fit of the experimental data represented as red squares while the black lines indicate the standard deviation of the triplicate measurements.

For the evaluation of the viability of the pre-lyophilisation, 100 μL of each of the L flasks were extracted and serially diluted in 1:10 concentrations in LB. This process was sequentially repeated 8 times until obtaining the lowest dilution with a final dilution factor of $1:10^8$. When the eight dilutions were ready ($1:10^1$, $1:10^2$, $1:10^3$, $1:10^4$, $1:10^5$, $1:10^6$, $1:10^7$, and $1:10^8$), three LB-agar Petri dishes were inoculated with 100 μL of each one.. All the plates were shaken in a circular and perpendicular pattern using laboratory glass beads to distribute the cells over the entire surface. These beads were later put into diluted bleach for further disinfection, while the plates were preserved in the 30 $^\circ\text{C}$ stove for around 2 days.

In parallel, different volumes (10, 15 and 25 mL) of the L flasks were introduced in 50 mL Falcon tubes. The Falcons were then centrifuged at 4000 RPM for 15 minutes in the centrifuge Gyrozen 1236R. The resulting supernatant was disposed of in diluted bleach while the precipitated bacteria pellet was kept inside the Falcon. Next, the pellets were redispersed in 5 mL of sucrose cryoprotectant (10 g of sucrose per 100 mL of distilled water), previously autoclaved, by using a vortex for 2-3 minutes. Resulting in three different bacteria:cryoprotectant ratios: 2:1, 3:1, and 5:1, whose viabilities are later assessed in this paper. When the pellet was completely resuspended in the

cryoprotectant, the content of the Falcon tubes was transferred to 10 mL glass vials. These were later covered with Parafilm and introduced into dry ice for some minutes until they were entirely frozen.

Freeze-drying

Once the samples of the vials were completely solidified, they were introduced into the Telstar LyoAlfa 15 freeze-drier after carefully perforating the lids to allow the vacuum inside them. The samples stayed in the machine for several days, even a week, until the state of the bacteria-cryoprotectant mixture looked crystallized and porous, like the one shown in Figure 3. Right after the vials were extracted from the freeze-drier, the Parafilm lids were removed as sterilized plastic stoppers were put on top of them and they were then kept at room temperature until the rehydration.

Rehydration of the lyophiles

Finally, for the rehydration, the stoppers were removed and the crystallised structure of the lyophile was grinded into powder. Next, 5 mL of LB medium were added and the mixture was softly mixed. The viability measurements of the rehydrated lyophile were executed following exactly the same previous procedure

described for serial dilutions applied to the pre-lyophile viability.

Figure 3: Picture of a glass vial containing 5 mL of lyophilised cryoprotectant with a concentration of 5:1 of bacteria inoculum.

RESULTS

Viability assessments were done 1-2 days after the inoculation of the Petri dishes following the Colony-Forming Units (CFU's) procedure, which is one of the most used methods for determining the number of viable cells in a given volume (the inoculum).^{16, 17} For colony counting, OpenCFU software was used together with manual counting in order to have redundancy in the measures.

Pre-lyophilisation viability

Although CFU's counting is typically restricted for counting less than 300 colonies per plate, this recommendation resides in the fact that merging colonies could be underestimated. However, the implementation of counting software enables a higher accuracy for colony counting for cases like the pre-lyophilisation viability we performed, where it happened to be higher than expected at the moment of the inoculation and therefore further dilutions were required for easier visual counting.

For instance, the Petri plate shown in Figure 4, corresponding to the $1:10^8$ dilution factor flask, could be correctly counted thanks to the implementation of the software tools mentioned.

Concerning the viability assessments of the pre-lyophile, mean values and standard deviation of viability measurements could be calculated due to triplicate plate seeding. In this case, $1:10^8$ dilution

factor was chosen for viability assessment, as it is the lowest dilution done for the pre-lyophile, while still presenting countable colonies. The results are shown in the next table.

Figure 4: Petri dish with $1:10^8$ dilution factor of the L3 flask. Blue squares represent each colony counted, red squares (top) are miscounts.

The pre-lyophile viability values shown in Table 1 exhibit a notably low standard deviation, indicating a high degree of precision and certainty in the measurement. This also corroborates the precision of automated counting applied to cell counting.

Table 1: Viability assessment for $1:10^8$ dilution factor of a 1:1 concentration pre-lyophile

No. of Colonies	Mean	Std. Deviation	$\cdot 10^{12}$ CFU's/mL
3173	3219,0	64,35	3,22
3310			
3174			

Viability of different concentration lyophiles

As mentioned above, different ratios of bacteria:cryoprotectant (2:1, 3:1, and 5:1) were tested. The viability results of these different-concentrated lyophiles, rehydrated 8 days after their lyophilisation, at dilution factor $1:10^4$ can be compared in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Plates of $1:10^4$ dilution for viability assessments of A) 2:1, B) 3:1 and C) 5:1 concentrations.

The data clearly reveal a remarkable disparity in the number of live cells between the rows. This observation is to be expected, as the concentration of the lyophile that was sown on the plates increases as one moves down the rows. To accurately determine the viability of each concentration, a CFU counting method combining manual and software tools was used. The resulting data are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Viability assessment for $1:10^8$ dilution factor of 2:1, 3:1 and 5:1 concentrations lyophiles after 8 days

Concentration	No. of Colonies	Mean	Std. Deviation	$\cdot 10^6$ CFU's/mL
2:1	106	99,3	8,06	9,93
	104			
	88			
3:1	81	81,3	3,68	8,13
	86			
	77			
5:1	201	206,3	66,24	20,6
	128			
	290			

Although values presented in Table 2 show that there is viability after lyophilising the samples, there are two anomalies to take care of for future batches. The first one is the notably high standard deviation of the 5:1 concentration, and the second one is the lesser viability

of the 3:1 concentration with respect to the viability of the 2:1 concentration.

To better notice this second anomaly, data collected in Table 3 shows the theoretical and experimental ratios between the viability of the different concentrations. If the experimental values of the ratios are consistent with the theoretical values, no loss is seen, however, the variation seen on the first ratio (2:1/3:1) signals a loss of viability on the 3:1 concentration.

Table 3: Theoretical and experimental ratios of viability between different concentrations

Ratio	Theoretical	Experimental
(2:1)/(3:1)	0,667	1,220
(3:1)/(5:1)	0,600	0,481
(2:1)/(5:1)	0,400	0,394

CONCLUSIONS

The spectrophotometry measurements carried out along this work have been key to plot the complete growth curve of *C. violaceum* from its beginning until the plateau phase. Having its growth characterized not only opens up the possibility to know exactly in which phase of the growth the bacteria are, but also allows us to predict up to a certain degree the moment when the *Quorum sensing* process begins. As a result, repeatability of future lyophilisation batches is granted, since it has been determined that lyophilisation must be executed when the bacteria is in the early exponential phase, as it is the point of higher cell growth.

On the other hand, preliminary results from CFU's viability assessments conducted before and after lyophilisation indicate a loss of bacteria corresponding to six orders of magnitude, however, this is comprehensible since the bacteria is exposed to stress during the freeze-drying process. However, it is relevant to study the evolution of the decay of the viable cells for long periods of time, representative of what the nominal duration of the mission is. To this aim, further lyophilised samples shall be prepared and viability tests shall be performed in order to determine whether the viability of the bacteria is still inside the required limits for the successful development of the mission.

In addition, the optimal bacteria concentration analyzed by the CFU viability assays in the lyophiles presented that there is a significant loss on viability when the cryoprotectant and bacterial culture mixture is in proportion 3/1 culture/cryoprotectant. Meanwhile, the usage of 5/1 and 2/1 proportions of bacterial culture/cryoprotectant get the expected values for each

trial. These values suggest that more concentrated bacteria: cryoprotectant proportions may show higher viability, being useful to our purpose, as the cell amount can be increased many times and still being kept within the expected values of viability, thus without killing the bacteria by overpopulation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Firstly, we would like to express our gratitude to the Xunta de Galicia and the ERDF for their financial support provided through grant GRC ED431C 2020/09, which enabled the realization of this study. We would also like to acknowledge the valuable collaboration of Dr. Isabel Pastoriza-Santos, the head of the Functional NanoBioMaterials group, and all members of the group for their contribution and assistance at different stages of this study. We also extend our appreciation to Dr. Gustavo Bodelón González, the head of the Synthetic Biology Group (SynBio), and all its members for their assistance in carrying out various parts of this work. Furthermore, we acknowledge the collaboration and contributions of Carmen Sieiro Vázquez from the Innovation in Agri-Food and Health area towards the development of this study. Lastly, we express our gratitude to Galina Pinzaru and Fátima Otero Dios from the CINBIO Research Centre for their assistance in different phases of this project.

In addition, we would like to recognize the contribution of Prof. Fernando Aguado Agelet and his research group in aerospace technology for their unwavering support during the evolution of the BIXO mission and for sharing their expertise in CubeSats missions. Together with our financial sponsors, they make possible all the scientific research emerging from UVigo SpaceLab.

REFERENCES

1. Camanzo Mariño, Alejandro & Diz-Folgar, Manuel & Vale-Xoubanova, Manuel & Castro, Pablo & Parafita, Pedro & Amaro-Losada, Lucía & Agelet, Fernando & Bodelon, Gustavo & Sieiro, Carmen & Pastoriza-Santos, Isabel & Pérez-Juste, Jorge. (2022). BIXO, a student-led CubeSat mission for education and astrobiology research.
2. Rutherford, Steven T, and Bonnie L Bassler. "Bacterial quorum sensing: its role in virulence and possibilities for its control." Cold Spring Harbor perspectives in medicine vol. 2,11 a012427. 1 Nov. 2012.
3. Vijay Kothari and Sakshi Sharma and Divya Padia. "Recent research advances on *Chromobacterium violaceum*". Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Medicine, vol. 10, No. 8, 2017.
4. Vogel, D., Mukkala, A.N., Ren, K., Lan, X., Li, Y., Velzen, E.V., Bruno, Almeida, Chanen, C., Miles, A., Haydaroglu, A., Gulab, A., Bhatia, A., Alejandro, Duque, Nickooie, A., Man, A., Barros, A., Zulfiqar, A., Shi, A., Quilumbango, A., Uderian, A., Xie, A., Nourimand, A., Saif, A., Datar, A., Dighe, A., Nowicki, A., Wong, A., Kwashigah, B., Makarchuk, B., Nero, B.W., Weng, B., Jasztrab, B., Brendan, Graham, Koehler, B., Richards, B., Moraldo, C., Dunn, C., Li, C.Y., Choi, D., Varshavsky, D., Sudarsan, D., Grande, E.M., Belhadfa, E., Gabriel, Sher, Blinn, H., Arshad, H., Wang, H., El-Halabi, H., Pervez, I., Berezny, J., Jaden, Reimer, Sheridan, J.W., Rock, J.R., Nicholls, J.G., Osborne, J.R., Gong, J., Hon, J., Joey, Capan, Smeal, J., Ramji, K.S., Korol, K.J., Le, K., Gwozdecky, K., Katie, Harris, Burnett, K., Chu, K., Shek, K.F., Tang, L., Faust, L., Zoubakina, L., Louis, Pahlavi, Talamo, L., Mehboob, M., Tkatchenko, M., Korte, M.D., Lorch, M., Silverman, M.R., Lin, M.J., Kim, M., Hirole, M., Zaman, M., Nikoo, Givehchian, Wang, N., Coskun, O., Samaha, P., Sukhnani, P.K., Malik, P., Priyank, K., Purohit, Sinnatamby, R.N., Shemesh, R., Howlader, R., Uraiqat, R., Khan, R., Rocco, Ruan, Bansal, R., Liang, R., Brown, R., Ngai, R., Song, R., Khan, S.O., Looper, S., Murray, S.K., Alazzam, S., Smith, S., Parikh, S., Mahendraker, S., Siddharth, S., Gopalan, Dey, S., Lau, S.C., Chung, S., Pararusam, S., Butt, T.A., Gharbiah, T.A., Deaibes, T., Binopal, T.S., Liu, T., Leung, T.S., Leung, T., Timothy, Yeung, Onuk, U., Mali, U., Farhadi, V., Nechita, V., Ferrie, W.S., & Zeng, Z. (2021). SSC21-WKII-09 HERON: Demonstrating a Novel Biological Platform for Small Satellite Missions.
5. Harandi, B.J., Ng, S., Liddell, L.C., Gentry, D.M., & Santa Maria, S.R. (2022). Fluidic-Based Instruments for Space Biology Research in CubeSats. *Frontiers in Space Technologies*.
6. Kitts, C.A., Hines, J.W., Agasid, E.F., Ricco, A.J., Yost, B.D., Ronzano, K., & Puig-Suari, J. (2006). The GeneSat-1 Microsatellite Mission A Challenge in Small Satellite Design.
7. Padgen, Michael & Chinn, Tori & Friedericks, Charlie & Lera, Matthew & Chin, Matthew & Parra, Macarena & Piccini, Matthew & Ricco, Antonio & Spremo, Stevan. (2020). The EcAMSat Fluidic System to Study Antibiotic Resistance in Low Earth Orbit: Development and Lessons Learned from Space Flight. *Acta*

- Astronautica. 173.
10.1016/j.actaastro.2020.02.031.
8. Matin, Ac & Wang, J-H & Keyhan, Mimi & Singh, Rachna & Benoit, Michael & Parra, Macarena & Padgen, Michael & Ricco, Antonio & Chin, Matthew & Friedericks, Charlie & Chinn, Tori & Cohen, Aaron & Henschke, Michael & Snyder, Timothy & Lera, Matthew & Ross, Shannon & Mayberry, Christina & Choi, Sungshin & Wu, Diana & Spremo, Stevan. (2017). Payload hardware and experimental protocol development to enable future testing of the effect of space microgravity on the resistance to gentamicin of uropathogenic *Escherichia coli* and its σ s-deficient mutant. *Life Sciences in Space Research*. 15. 10.1016/j.lssr.2017.05.001.
 9. Kitts, C. & Ronzano, Karolyn & Rasay, Richard & Mas, Ignacio & Acain, Jose & Neumann, Michael & Bica, Laura & Mahacek, Paul & Minelli, Giovanni & Beck, Erin & Li, Steve & Gamp, Brian & Agnew, Seamus & Shepard, John & Hines, John & Agasid, Elwood & Friedericks, Charlie & Piccini, Matthew & Parra, Macarena & McGinnis, Michael. (2009). Initial Flight Results from the PharmaSat Biological Microsatellite Mission.
 10. Santa Maria, Sergio & Marina, Diana & Tieze, Sofia & Liddell, Lauren & Bhattacharya, Sharmila. (2020). BioSentinel: Long-Term *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* Preservation for a Deep Space Biosensor Mission. *Astrobiology*. 10.1089/ast.2019.2073.
 11. Minelli, Giovanni & Ricco, Antonio & Beasley, Christopher & Hines, John & Agasid, Elwood & Yost, Bruce & Squires, David & Friedericks, Charlie & Piccini, Matthew & Defouw, Greg & McIntyre, Mike & Ricks, Robert & Parra, Macarena & Diaz-Aguado, Millan & Timucin, Linda & Henschke, Mike & Lera, Matthew & Tan, Ming & Cohen, Mike & Bica, Laura. (2010). O/OREOS Nanosatellite: A Multi-Payload Technology Demonstration.
 12. Broeckx, G., Vandenheuvel, D., Claes, I. J., Lebeer, S., & Kiekens, F. (2016). Drying techniques of probiotic bacteria as an important step towards the development of novel pharmabiotics. *International journal of pharmaceutics*, 505(1-2), 303-318.
 13. Stephen, F. (1995). Freeze-drying and cryopreservation of bacteria. In *Cryopreservation and freeze-drying protocols* (pp. 21-30). Humana Press, Totowa, NJ.
 14. Heckly, R. J. (1961). Preservation of bacteria by lyophilisation. In *Advances in applied microbiology* (Vol. 3, pp. 1-76). Academic Press.
 15. Wan Salim, Wan W. Amani & Park, Joon Hyeong & Rickus, J.L. & Rademacher, A. & Ricco, Antonio & Schooley, A. & Benton, J. & Wickizer, Brittany & Martinez, A. & Mai, N. & Rasay, Mike & Porterfield, D. & Brownston, L. & Cote, M. & Defouw, G. & Henschke, M. & Kitts, C. & Luzzi, E. & Perez, M. & Sweet, A.. (2014). SPORESAT: A NANOSATELLITE PLATFORM LAB-ON-A-CHIP SYSTEM FOR INVESTIGATING GRAVITY THRESHOLD OF FERN SPORE SINGLE-CELL CALCIUM CURRENTS. 111-114. 10.31438/trf.hh2014.32.
 16. Jett, B. D., Hatter, K. L., Huycke, M. M., & Gilmore, M. S. (1997). Simplified agar plate method for quantifying viable bacteria. *BioTechniques*, 23(4), 648-650.
 17. Sieuwerts, S., de Bok, F. A., Mols, E., de vos, W. M., & Vlieg, J. E. (2008). A simple and fast method for determining colony forming units. *Letters in applied micr*